

The Whispers

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I am a Mountain

Sun flames my head,
Fog is unfriendly to me,
The wind is knocking me down,
Everyone is so impolite to me.

Left Left, Left me alone,
Oh! My lonely soul,
No mortal comes anymore,
I'm useless, I'm useless!

Thirst, hunger torment to weaken me,
Rift breathtaking,
For I've lost my crown,
Left Left, Left me alone!

For this is my story,
I long, weep with no tears,
For morning flutes unheard,
Oh! My lovely family!

O mortals return my crown,
Let blanketed pips grow greater,
For I've a life too!

Rosita Ddungdung

Lecturer in English
